

CyberSecDome

An innovative **Virtual Reality** based intrusion detection, incident investigation and response, approach for enhancing the **resilience, security, privacy and accountability** of complex and heterogeneous **digital systems** and infrastructures

CyberSecDome at a glance

The "**CyberSecDome**" is a comprehensive solution that covers the entire digital infrastructure, addressing the challenges of a highly interconnected digital environment.

It enables stakeholders to collaborate effectively in handling cyber events, and identifying threats and risks.

Moreover, it facilitates the development of comprehensive response and recovery strategies, with the primary goal of reducing the impact of cyber attacks, including potential disruptions or destruction of critical digital infrastructure.

CyberSecDome's Pilots

Hellenic Telecommunications Organisation:

OTE brings in its nation-wide telecommunications network, its advanced telecommunication services, and its 24/7 Security Operations Center. The CyberSecDome solution will be validated on OTE's infrastructure in terms of its efficacy in managing sensitive data and providing managed security services.

Athens International Airport:

AIA brings in a dynamic cyber-physical environment, with diverse stakeholders and services. The CyberSecDome solution will be validated on AIA's infrastructure in terms of its ability to protect critical infrastructures, as well as provide valuable insights for refining and validating cybersecurity solutions in a challenging real-world setting.

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CyberSecDome

Consortium Members

Technical
University
of Munich

AIRBUS
CYBERSECURITY

li.u LINKÖPING
UNIVERSITY

AEGIS
IT RESEARCH

ΠΟΛΥΤΕΧΝΕΙΟ
ΚΡΗΤΗΣ
TECHNICAL
UNIVERSITY
OF CRETE

Cyberalytics

CyberSecDome will run an **Open Call**, focused on mid-caps and SMEs with an interest in adopting and using advanced and innovative cybersecurity solutions, allocating a budget of 1,5M€ ensuring a wider reach across the EU Digital Infrastructures ecosystem

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Contact us: info@cybersecdome.eu

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